

Major and Minor Pest Species in Agricultural Area of Kyaing Tong University Campus

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Abstract

The present study was conducted in Kyaing Tong University Campus and nearby yards. This study was conducted from August, 2015 to September, 2016 in Kyaing Tong University Campus. The present work was the first attempt to describe the insect pests of Kyaing Tong Township. The objectives of this study were to identify and study the morphology and feeding habit of insect pest species in the study areas which will be helpful to the gardeners and future researchers working on the pest insects in this region. According to results, 13 different species from 13 genera, 11 families, four orders, belonging to class Insecta were recorded. This present work is impossible to cover all the insect pest species of study sites due to the limited time. Further investigation and identification of the remaining species in this region are also needed.

Key words: mouth parts, tibia spurs, rostrum, ovipositor, nymphs

Introduction

Many insect pests damage growing crops, fruits and vegetable farms, the damage they cause annually and the number of such insect pests is innumerable.

There are many orders of insect pests which attack the cruciferous crop like Orthoptera (grasshopper) Hemiptera (bugs), Lepidoptera (butterflies and moths), Coleoptera (beetles and weevils), Hymenoptera (ants, bees, wasps). (Morris and Warterhouse, 2001).

Order Hemiptera belong to division Exopterygota, simple body change during growth (incomplete metamorphosis). Bugs are the members of this order (Imms, 1964). The order Coleoptera and Lepidoptera belong to division Endopterygota (complete matamorphosis). Beetles, butterflies and moths are the members of these orders. (Borroret *al.*, 1992). The order Coleoptera with over 220,000 described species ranks as the largest order of insects and contains the most common and important stored product pests.

These two major groups of insects harbor the mostly economically important pests. They attack crops both in the field and stores. Crop damage by Lepidoptera is only done by larvae. In the case of Coleoptera, both the larvae and adult often feed on the crops and make considerable damage (Borrer and White, 1976).

Sometimes, the food eaten by immature stages and the adult is the same. But larval stage has very different feeding habits. Different species of insects eat all sorts and parts of plants-roots, stems or leaves, sap or blossoms, seeds or fruits, many flower and secretions of animals and the scavenger insects consume dead animals and plants (Imms, 1964).

Most insects are divided into two broad categories by mouth part type, namely chewing and sucking. Chewing insect's bites and chew plant parts creating holes and tunnels in leaves, stems, twigs and fruits. Sucking insect pierce plants with slender, sharp-pointed mouth parts and suck plants sap. Withdrawl of the sap results in minute white brown or red spotting on leaves, fruits or twigs. It may also cause curling leaves, deformed fruits or general wilting, browning and dying of the entire plant (Blackely, 2010).

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Examples of chewing insects include dragon flies, grasshoppers most wasps, termites, caterpillars and beetles. Some insects do not have chewing mouthparts as adults but do chew solid food when they feed while they still are larvae. Insects with piercing-sucking mouth parts include some flies (think mosquitoes), fleas, true bugs and their relatives.

Bugs have piercing, sucking mouthpart in the form of a long rostrum made up of slender stylets sheathed by the labium. Many bugs that suck plant sap are serious crop pest (Kindersley, 2000).

The life history of some insects are simple completing all life stages on the plant while others are complex having some life stages under the soil below the host plant, sometimes alternation of host plants. (Kulkarni, 2006).

Inside the Kyaing Tong University campus and its nearby yards are grown various agricultural plants, such as rice, corn, soybean, pigeon pea etc. and flower plants, principally rose, jasmine. The insect pests cause various damages to their respective trees and plants. To control the attack of insect pests by any means, the biology of these pests should be known.

As there are no previous records on the localized study of the occurrence of insect pests, this research paper would provide the essential step for the control of insect pests and the necessary arrangements we can be made to ensure the successful production of crops. The more we know about a pest, the easier and more successful pest management becomes.

The present research work focused on the following objectives:

- to identify insect pests in agricultural field
- to study the morphology and feeding habit of some insect pests

Materials and methods

Study area

The present study was conducted in Kyaing Tong University Campus and nearby yards, Kyaing Tong Township. It located 21°17'30"N and 99°36' 30" in East Shan State. Kyaing Tong University Campus covers an area of 33538 square km; from east to west, it is 289.56m, from south to north the distance is 115.83m.

Study period

This study was conducted from August 2015 to June 2016 in Kyaing Tong University Campus.

Collection of specimens

The specimens were collected once a week early in the morning and late in the evening. The insect pests were caught by bare hand while resting or feeding on crops. The varied sizes and stage of insect pests were collected in surrounding area of crop cultivation and in the crop field.

Preservation of the specimens

The collected specimens were put in plastic bottles and brought back to the laboratory at Department of Zoology for identification and further investigations. Photographs of studied pest species were taken while they were alive to avoid colour changes and deformation. The damaged or infested parts of the plant due to the pests were also noted down and photographed with digital camera in the crop field.

Identification of collected specimens

Identification and classification of collected specimens were based on Imms (1964) and Hill (1983).

A. Corn field

B. Pigeon field

C. Mustard field

D. Soya bean field

E. Pumpkin field

F. Egg-plant

Plate.1 Various crop fields in study area

Result

A total of 13 species, 13 genera, 11 families, 4 orders, belonging to the class Insecta were recorded (Table 1).

Systematic position of studied species

- | | | |
|------------|---|--|
| Kingdom | - | Animalia |
| Phylum | - | Arthropoda |
| Class | - | Insecta |
| Order | - | Orthoptera |
| Family | - | Gryllidae |
| Genus | - | <i>Brachytrypes</i> |
| 1. Species | - | <i>B. portentosus</i> Randell, 1904 |
| Genus | - | <i>Gryllus</i> |
| 2. Species | - | <i>G. pensylvanicus</i> Burmeister, 1838 |
| Family | - | Gryllotalpidae |
| Genus | - | <i>Gryllotalpa</i> |
| 3. Species | - | <i>G. orientalis</i> Burmeister, 1838 |
| Family | - | Acrididae |
| Genus | - | <i>Oxya</i> |
| 4. Species | - | <i>O. japonia</i> (Thunberg, 1815) |
| Family | - | Tettigoniidae |
| Genus | - | <i>Atractomorpha</i> |
| 5. Species | - | <i>A. crenulata</i> Fabricius, 1761 |
| Genus | - | <i>Neoconocephalus</i> |
| 6. Species | - | <i>N. ensinger</i> Fabricius, 1761 |
| Order | - | Hemiptera |
| Family | - | Cicadidae |
| Genus | - | <i>Neotibicen</i> |
| 7. Species | - | <i>N. linnei</i> (Smith & Grassbeck, 1907) |
| Family | - | Aphididae |
| Genus | - | <i>Aphis</i> spp: |
| 8. Species | - | <i>Aphis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) |
| Family | - | Pyrrhocoridae |
| Genus | - | <i>Dindymus</i> |
| 9. Species | - | <i>D. versicolor</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1853) |
| Family | - | Alydidae |
| Genus | - | <i>Leptocorisa</i> |

10. Species - *L. oratorius* (Fabricius, 1794)
 Order - Lepidoptera
 Family - Syntomidae
 Genus - *Syntomoides*
11. Species - *S. imacon* (Cramer, 1780)
 Order - Coleoptera
 Family - Scarabaeidae
 Genus - *Adoretus*
12. Species - *A. sinicus* Burmeister, 1855
 Family - Chrysomelidae
 Genus - *Aphthona*
13. Species - *A. flava* Guillebeau, 1894

Description of the recorded pest species

1. Scientific name - *Brachytrypes portentosus* Randell, 1904
 Common name - Big Head Cricket, pa-yit
 (Plate. 2, A)

Description

The head is relatively large and approximately rectangular in shape and hangs vertically downwards. Long slender antennae and a pair of small spherical compound eyes are present. The two pairs of forward legs are shorter and approximately equal in size but the hind pair is comparatively longer and larger in size. The tibia is provided with a series of tibia spurs, functioning both as an offensive and defensive organ. The females can be distinguished from the males by the presence of along ovipositor at the terminal end of the broad abdomen.

Damage

They destroy the crop plant by digging the soil and root zone. Crickets are omnivorous, when deprived of their natural diet; they accept a wide range of organic food stuffs. Some species are completely herbivorous, feeding on flowers fruit, and leaves with ground-based species consuming seedlings, grasses, pieces of leaf and the shoots of young plants.

2. Scientific name - *Gryllus pensylvanicus* Burmeister, 1838
 Common name - Fall field cricket
 (Plate.2, B)

Description

Adults reach 15-25 millimeters (0.6-1.0 in) and the coloration ranges from dark black to dark brown, although some specimens show a slight reddish tint. The black antennae tend to be longer than the body span of the species. Their hindermost legs are much enlarged and are used by the cricket for powerful and rapid jumping. The hind wings of the field and brightly pigmented.

Damage

G. pennsylvanicus is omnivorous and has been shown to be a significant predator of both seeds and invertebrates. Large populations of field crickets cause significant damage to agricultural crops, and when this species enters houses (typically in the late summer and early fall) wool, cotton, silk, nylon, rubber and leather material may be consumed. A field cricket must eat its body weight or more in food every day.

3. Scientific name - *Gryllotalpa orientalis* Burmeister, 1838
 Common name - Mole cricket
 (Plate.2, C)

Description

Body is cylindrical, covered with short, fine hairs, plump, dull brown, paler beneath, very pubescent, about 30mm long. Head well developed, heavily sclerotised, short filiform antennae, small eyes and ocelli, a large oblong pronotum, with biting and chewing mouth parts. Fore legs enlarged, shovel-like modified both for digging and to act like a pair of scissors for cutting of small roots, fore wings are thickened and leathery, membranous hind wings folded and hidden under fore wing. A long ovipositor is present at the terminal end of the abdomen in the female.

Damage

They are adapted for underground life. It is a polyphagous pest, damaging crops by gnawing their roots. The cricket gnaws roots and tubers and causes damage to wheat, barley, oats, rice, maize, beans, vegetable crops, potatoes and sugar beet. Damage is sometimes done to rice crops in raised nursery beds or in upland conditions. In wetland rice, the crickets can be seen swimming between plants.

4. Scientific name - *Oxya japonica* (Thunberg, 1815)
 Common name - Short-horned grasshopper
 (Plate.2, D)

Description

The body of *Oxya japonica* is bright green with a yellow-green stripe running from the head along the back. A black stripe runs along each side of the body. The male is about 19mm long and the female is about 28mm. The body of the nymph is green. Two narrow red brown bands run down its back from the compound eyes to the base of the wings.

Damage

Most grasshopper species that occur in rice fields were none swarming and consequently cause minimal damage. When they become abundant locusts can destroy a rice crop. Grasshoppers can damage rice at all stages of crop growth. *Oxya* spp. are general feeders consuming foliage of grass species in addition to rice. The nymphs and adults feed on rice leaves and nurseries suffer the most when attacked. The entire plant dies if the attack is severe. If the emerging inflorescence is attacked the resulting grains become chafy.

5. Scientific name - *Atractomorpha crenulata* Fabricius, 1761

Common name - Short-horned grasshopper
(Plate.2, E)

Description

The body of the adult is long and slender, green in colour. Antennae are short and stout narrower than the width of the antennae. Head and pronotum with the sides slightly sloping, crenulated behind the eyes, the crenulation often pale or pink; prosternum with and obtusely founded tubercle. This grasshopper has an arrow head and 'V' shape antennae. The hind legs are adapted for jumping with greatly femurs. Tegmina pointed, extending for one fourth of their length beyond than tegmina. Abdomen is smooth with rosy. The background color of body is green white the legs are brown. The size is about 30mm long. The males are smaller than females.

Damage

The short horned grasshopper is the pest of eggplants, pumpkin and gourd plants especially it attacks their seedlings and it feeds on the leaves. It can defoliate trees and eat smaller plants to the ground. It causes serious damage to crops and ornamental plants their great abundance can be a nuisance.

6. Scientific name - *Neoconocephalus ensiger* Fabricius, 1761
Common name - Cone-head Katydid
(Plate.2, F)

Description

Most katydids are generally green, but brown, white and even pink varieties have been found. Adult katydid has 2 pairs of wings that are shaped and colored like leaves. They also have powerful back legs for jumping and strong jaw. Katydid is shaped like grasshoppers and crickets but have larger antennae. Females are usually larger than males and have a long sharp structure at the end of the abdomen. This looks like a stinger, but it is actually an ovipositor.

Damage

They can damage a large quantity of fruit in short time. They feed on leaves or fruit. Katydid do not eat the whole fruit. It chews on leaves. All katydids are camouflaged to blend with the leaves they feed on.

7. Scientific name - *Neotibicen linnei* (Smith & Grassbeck, 1907)
Common name - Cicada (Tree cricket)
(Plate.3, A)

Description

The bodies are wedge-shaped, the head very broad, eyes slightly bulging at the sides, the abdomen tapering rapidly behind short antennae and membranous front wings. The forewing are longer than body, lens-shaped, glistening, prominently veined, the hind pair half as long. The face is prolonged downward and backward 'V' shaped to the base of the slender,

stiff labium. The body is generally patterned with olive-green, reddish-yellow or whitish primrose, irregularly shaped.

Damage

The cicada is the very long life of the young in the periodical cicada, which spends as slowly growing nymphs underground, sucking the sap from the roots of trees. After this long subterranean existence they emerge in the form best known, the winged adults. The adults sometimes damage trees by splintering the twigs as they lay their eggs. Adults of *N. linnei* feed on sap from trees using their piercing and sucking mouthparts to reach the xylem of a branch. They are not host specific. As nymphs, they feed on sap from the roots of all trees.

8. Scientific name - *Aphis* spp: Linnaeus, 1758

Common name - Aphids
(Plate.3, B)

Description

Aphids are soft-bodied, pear-shaped bugs with piercing mouthparts that are used to suck out plant fluids. They can be green, pink, black or gray. Sometimes it looks like wearing a fluffy white coat. Most are smaller than 3mm long. Head is pointed and downward for feeding. Antennae are 5-6 segmented compound and simple eyes are present. Walking legs are skinny. Thorax and abdomen appear fused. Most aphids have conical tail pipes.

Damage

Adult *Aphis* feed on pollen and nectar. They are found on leaves, petioles, flowers, and roots and reduce plant vigor. Aphids are highly mobile and abundant. Aphids are typically nuisance pests. These pests generally appear in May and June. They feed by sucking the juices from young shoots, buds, and leaves. Various symptoms can indicate the presence of aphids. Leaves are often curled, puckered, or stunted. They will also turn yellow or brown and fall prematurely. Flowers are sometimes misshapen and have streaked petals. Black sooty mould will also appear as a result of honeydew produced by the aphids. Aphids can carry viral diseases, which can be harmful to roses.

9. Scientific name - *Dindymus versicolor* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1853)

Common name - Cotton Strainer bug
(Plate.3, C)

Description

Dindymusversicolor commonly called the harlequin bug, is a species of cotton stainer bug (red bug) found in south-eastern Australia and Tasmania. In nor the central districts of Victoria it is sometimes colloquially known as the 'Sex Beetle'.An attractive insect, up to 12mm long with a black head and bands on the fore wing and orange/red elsewhere. When the wings are folded two red triangles-appear legs are relatively long.

Damage

These sucking insects have a reputation as a pest in the garden, damaging a wide range of plants. They are known to damage a variety of crops and ornamental. The New South Wales

Department of primary Industries (Agriculture) reported that they attack cotton, stone fruits, fig, grape, strawberry, vegetable, dahlia and violets.

10. Scientific name - *Leptocorisa oratorius* (Fabricius, 1794)
 Common name - Rice ear head bug or Paddy bug
 (Plate.3, D)

Description

The bug gives off an unpleasant smell in defense. Major pest to the rice plant (*Oryza sativa*), as they feed on the plants and killing it in the process. Around 2cm length, with long legs and a long proboscis. It is brownish green in color.

Damage

L. oratorius is a major rice pests which feed on the sap of stems and rice seeds. *L. oratorius* preferred rice to grass for feeding and oviposition. Rice bug adults and nymphs have piercing-sucking mouth parts and feed by sucking fluid from florets and soft grains. Grain in the milk stage is preferred. Damaged grains are discolored or peaky. Peaky grains may break during milling.

11. Scientific name - *Syntomoides imaon* (Cramer, 1780)
 Common name - Handmaden moth
 (Plate.3, E)

Description

The moth has a wingspan of 34mm. It's wings are black with some transparent windows, the hind wing is smaller than fore wing. It has black abdomen with two orange rings. The antennae are black with white color at the top. The fore wing has large hyaline patches, one filling the cell, another filling nearly the whole inferno-median interspaced, one at junction of veins 2 and 3, two suboptimal and two sub marginal.

Damage

S. imaonis a polyphagous pest that causes damage to various crops. *Syntomoides* (*Syntomidae-Lepidoptesa*) caterpillars feed on several agricultural and non-agricultural crop plants and affect the growth and yield of the crops.

12. Scientific name - *Adoretus sinicus* (Burmeister, 1855)
 Common name - Chinese Rose Beetles
 (Plate.3, F)

Description

The adult beetle is oblong, oval, reddish brown and covered with creamy, dense, scale-like setae, giving the beetle an overall grayish appearance. Body length varies from 10-12mm in length. The characteristic interregnal defoliation pattern of the Chinese rose beetle is caused by the beetle's unusual mouthparts. The labrum is produced ventrally at the middle and forms a tooth-like process. This process completely separates the mandibles and maxillae into two independent chewing apparatus that are incapable of meeting in the middle.

Damage

Major crops attacked include asparagus, beans, broccoli, cabbage, cacao, Chinese broccoli, Chinese cabbage, corn, cotton cucumber, egg plant, flowering white cabbage, ginger,

grape, green bean, okra, rose, soybeans, strawberry and sweet potato. Adults feed on plant foliage at night, creating a lace-like or shot with holes appear once on leaves by feeding on plant tissue between leaf veins. In severe cases most leaves are skeletonized.

13. Scientific name - *Aphthona flava* (Guillebeau, 1894)

Common name - Flea beetles

(Plate.3, G)

Description

Aphthona are flea beetles, meaning they have enlarged hind legs for jumping away from potential danger. Adults are orange coppery colour, two to four mm long. Females are slightly larger than males.

Damage

Larvae feed on root hairs, young roots and parts of the main root, reducing the plant's ability to absorb moisture and accumulate nutrients. Adult foliar feeding is quite impressive as they consume small leaves and buds. Foliar feeding can impede the plant's photosynthesis and can cause nutrient starvation. *A. flava*'s ability to drop and leap away when threatened enables the adult to survive in a grazed environment. Adult will feed gregariously on the leaves and bracts of leafy spurge.

(A) *Brachytrypes portentosus*

(B) *Gryllus pensylvanicus*

(C) *Gryllotalpa orientalis*

(D) *Oxya japonica*

(E) *Atractomorpha crenulata*

(F) *Neoconocephalus ensiger*

(G) *Neotibicen linnei*

(H) *Aphis*

Plate .2 Recorded pest species of order – Orthoptera

(I) *Dindymus versicolor*

(J) *Leptocoris oratorius*

(K) *Syntomoides imaon*

(L) *Adoretus sinicus*

(M) *Aphthona flava*

Plate .3 Recorded pest species of order Hemiptera, Coleoptera, Lepidoptera

Table. 2. Types of mouth parts and damaged parts of plants

No.	Recorded	Mouth parts	Major/Minor	Damage area of plant
1.	<i>Brachytrypes portentosus</i>	Chewing and biting	Major	root, seed, leaves
2.	<i>Gryllus pensylvanicus</i>	Chewing and biting	Major	root, seed, leaves
3.	<i>Gryllotalpa orientalis</i>	Chewing and biting	Major	root, seed, leaves
4.	<i>Oxya japonica</i>	Chewing and biting	Minor	leaves
5.	<i>Atractomorpha crenulata</i>	Chewing and biting	Minor	seed, leaves
6.	<i>Neococephalus ensiger</i>	Chewing and biting	Minor	fruit, leaves
7.	<i>Neotibicen linnei</i>	Sucking type	Major in nymph	root, twig
8.	<i>Aphis</i>	Sucking type	Major	plant, leaves
9.	<i>Dindymus versicolor</i>	Sucking type	Major	Plant, leaves
10.	<i>Leptocoris oratorius</i>	Sucking type	Major	flower, seed
11.	<i>Syntomoides imaon</i>	Sucking type	Major	plant
12.	<i>Adoretus sinicus</i>	chewing and biting	Minor	leaves
13.	<i>Aphthona flava</i>	chewing and biting	Major	root, leaves, bracts

Discussion

The present study covered 13 species of insects falling under one Class, four Orders and 11 Families. Among these, six species were Orthoptera, four species were Hemiptera, two species were Coleoptera and only one species was Lepidoptera (Table 1).

Kyaing Tong environs have many agricultural land especially paddy and cultivated seasonal corn, thick vegetation bushes and shrubs. Rose plants are flourish in this region. There could favour the occurrence of different pest species.

In this study, the percentage of species composition of Order Orthoptera was 46%, Order Hemiptera 31%, Order Coleoptera 15% and Order Lepidoptera 8% were recorded at Kyaing Tong University.

In this present study, the insect pests are divided into two broad categories by mouth parts, chewing and sucking type. The chewing and biting type insects are under Order Orthoptera and Coleoptera. Sucking types are found in Order Hemiptera and Order Lepidoptera.

In damage of plant parts due to insect pests are stem, leave, root, flower and seeds. In the present study the cause of damage symptoms due to chewing and sucking insects are agreed with the Blackely, 2000.

A number of species were collected from the paddy, corn and soya bean fields and shrubs such as rose plants.

The chewing mouthpart type insects feed on leaves and bite the hole in the leaves of seedling and sometimes chew the young stem.

Adoretus sinicus and *Aphthona flava* feed on the leaves in the host plants and produces pit-like hole or shot hole of the anterior, although they also chew along leaf margin and stems. (Table.2)

Neotibicen linnei, *Aphis*, *Dindymus versicolor*, *Leptocorisa oratorius* and *Syntomiodes imacon* suck the sap from the host plants and reduce the vigor of the plants. They serve infestation; the leaves turn yellow and drop off. *Gryllotalpa orientalis* and *Gryllus pensylvanicus* feeds on the roots of plants, tubers and rhizomes and damaging crops by gnawing their roots. Crops have been attacked by these crickets and their tunneling activities have caused damage to the banks of irrigation ditches. Damage is sometimes done to rice crops in raised nursery beds or in upland conditions. They are adapted for underground life. *Oxya japonica*, *Atractomorpha crenulata* and *Neococephalus ensiger* attack vegetable crops including cucurbitaceous plants and ornamentals. They attack seedlings and it feeds on the leaves. *Brachytrypes portentosus* (house crickets) are nocturnal and seasonal insects.

Leptocorisa oratorius feeds primarily on graminaceous plants such as rice, wheat and sugarcane. Excessive feeding can cause yellow spots on the leaves. This reduces photosynthesis and in extreme case can damage the vascular system of the plant. Puncture holes also serve as points of entry for several plant pathogens, such as fungus that cause sheath rot disease. The most economically important damage is caused when the adults and nymphs feed on the developing grains. Such damage causes discoloration of the grains, which reduces market quality. (Hill, 2008).

Aphis causes discolored spots and heavily plant can show large necrotic areas sometimes resulting in the damaged of entire leaf bract, and flower. Honey dew, a sticky liquid excreted by the aphid, covers the foliage and often colonized by black saprophytic fungi, hampering respiration and photosynthesis. Thus, the present findings were agreed that of Honda *et al.*, (1990) who stated that the population dynamics of aphids were related to virus transmission.

The present research work is not claimed complete work as the given time is limited for this study, but the information present in this work could be value to make necessary arrangements for the control of insect pests and ensure the successful production of crops. To know more about insect pest, long term monitoring is needed for more actual information.

Conclusion

The present work was the first attempt to describe the insect pests of Kyaing Tong Township. The objectives of this study were to identify and study the morphology and feeding

habit of insect pest species in the study areas which will be helpful to the gardeners and future researchers working on the pest insects in this region. For this purpose a preliminary survey was carried out. According to results, 13 different species from 13 genera, 11 families, four orders, belonging to class Insecta were recorded. Among them 10 species were major pests. This present work is impossible to cover all the insect pest species of study sites due to the limited time. Further investigation and identification of the remaining species in this region are also needed.

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